

PHYTOCHEMICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION OF *GOSSYPIUM HERBACEUM*: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Gossypium herbaceum L. (Levant cotton) is an old cotton species that has been used in traditional medicine for centuries.^[1,2] It contains macronutrients like carbohydrates, proteins, and fats, as well as secondary metabolites such as gossypol, flavonoids (including gossypin and quercetin), tannins (like proanthocyanidins), terpenoids, alkaloids, steroids, and saponins.^[1,3,4] Research shows it has strong antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritis, antidiabetic, hypolipidemic, wound healing, anticonvulsant, antifertility, and other effects.^[2,5] These results suggest *G. herbaceum* has therapeutic potential and that more research is needed to understand its active compounds and possible clinical uses.

KEYWORDS: *Gossypium herbaceum*, Phytochemical profile, Gossypol, Flavonoids, Pharmacological activities.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants remain important sources for new drugs. *Gossypium herbaceum* (*Malvaceae*) is valued in Asian, African, and Unani medicine. In Unani and Ayurveda, it is used to increase milk production and support reproductive health, while folk medicine uses it for respiratory, digestive, and metabolic issues. Its seeds and leaves are rich in vitamins, especially vitamin E, and contain pain-relieving compounds.^[1,6] This review looks at *G.*

herbaceum's botany, phytochemistry, and pharmacology to summarize current knowledge and highlight areas for future research.

Taxonomy and Botanical Classification

Gossypium herbaceum L. belongs to the Kingdom Plantae, Order *Malvales*, Family *Malvaceae*, Genus *Gossypium*, and Species *herbaceum*. It is also known as Levant cotton, Syrian cotton, or Indian/Oriental cotton. Local names include Karpas, Kapasi, Bonnara, Kapāsā (Hindi), Pambadāna (Unani), and Habbul-qutn (Arabic).^[1] Other names like *Gossypium indicum* and *G. capitatum* reflect its wide cultivation. As an Old World diploid cotton, it is closely related to *G. arboreum* and has been grown alongside *G. hirsutum* and *G. barbadense*.^[2]

Botanical Description

G. herbaceum is a shrubby, upright perennial that grows 2 to 8 feet tall, with a thick woody stem and soft, hairy branches. Its leaves are alternate and palmately lobed, usually with 3 to 7 lobes that are ovate to broadly oblong and have serrated edges. The flowers are large and colorful, with yellow petals (sometimes white, red, or purple) and often a dark purple or red spot at the base. The calyx is glandular at the base.^[6,7,8] The fruit is a spiny capsule, called a cotton ball, that ripens to an ovate, pointed shape. After removing the fibers, the seeds are ovoid, 5–20 mm long, dark brown or nearly black, and have a fleshy kernel with a hull and some remaining fibers.^[1] Under the microscope, the root shows a multilayered cortex and phloem, lysigenous cavities, and medullary rays. Powdered root or leaf contains lignified fibers, stone cells, calcium oxalate crystals, and some starch grains.^[9] The plant is grown throughout Asia and Europe, including India, Pakistan, China, Persia, and the Mediterranean.^[7,8] In India, most farming occurs in semi-arid states such as Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, and Uttar Pradesh.^[10] The plant thrives in arid to subhumid tropics and subtropics, tolerating drought and heat.^[2,11] It prefers well-drained, sandy to loamy soils and is grown as an annual or short-lived perennial in cultivation, though wild types can live perennially.

Traditional and Ethnomedicinal Uses

G. herbaceum has a long history of use in traditional medicine. The seeds are well known for increasing breast milk and are also used for back pain and neurosis. The root bark is considered an aphrodisiac and is used to treat sexual weakness and amenorrhea.^[1,6,12] The

leaves are applied as a poultice or juice to help heal wounds, cuts, and bleeding.^[9] Other uses include treating diarrhea, dysentery (using seed decoction), and dyspepsia.^[1,6]

- **Reproductive:** relief of dysmenorrhea, reduction of sperm count, usage of contraception (antispermatogenic action).

- **Metabolic/Other:** antidiabetic (leaf or root infusion), overall weakness, fever, earache (otalgia), and skin conditions.^[1]

Many of these uses are recorded in Unani medicine, such as seeds for breastfeeding and leaves for childhood diarrhea^[1,2] and in Ayurvedic texts like Kapāsam and Tundakesi.^[1,12] Folk healers also use the plant to relieve pain and as a remedy for snakebite, using juice from the leaves or seeds.^[6] These traditional claims have inspired modern pharmaceutical research.

Phytochemical Profile

7.1 Primary Metabolites

The oilseed kernel of *G. herbaceum* is rich in lipids, making up about 20-25% of its weight, and contains many unsaturated fatty acids. GC-MS analysis shows that linoleic acid is the main fatty acid in the leaves (about 33–36% of the total oil), along with a good amount of vitamin E (α -tocopherol).^[13] The oil also contains oleic, palmitic, and stearic acids. Cottonseed protein is highly nutritious, with about 78% digestibility and a biological value of 91%. Cottonseed meal is about 40% fiber and has plenty of carbohydrates like cellulose and starch. Both seeds and leaves have B-complex vitamins and minerals such as phosphorus, calcium, and magnesium.^[9] In summary, *G. herbaceum* seeds are high in linoleic acid, vitamin E, and protein, while the leaves provide dietary fiber and carbohydrates.

7.2 Secondary Metabolites

Many studies have shown that *G. herbaceum* contains a wide range of secondary metabolites. The main groups include.

- **Polyphenols:** The hallmark compound is gossypol – a dimeric phenolic sesquiterpenoid with two aldehyde groups (0.4–2.0% in seed).^[1] Gossypol is present in seed, root, and leaf pigment glands and has been related to a variety of bioactivities, including antifertility, anticancer, and antibacterial properties.^[2,3,14] Other phenolics include flavonoids (quercetin, kaempferol, apigenin glycosides, and gossypin),^[2,15] which have antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. Leaves contain condensed tannins (proanthocyanidins), which hydrolyse to produce cyanidin and delphinidin.^[4]

- **Alkaloids:** Though not as abundant as polyphenols, alkaloids have been detected in leaf extracts of *G. herbaceum*^[13] Their specific identities are not well documented, but they may contribute to the observed CNS effects.
- **Terpenoids and Steroids:** Triterpenoids and phytosterols (β -sitosterol, ergosterol, stigmasterol) occur in seeds and leaves. Cottonseed oil's unsaponifiable fraction includes these steroids along with gossypol.^[1] Monoterpenes such as caryophyllene have been identified by GC-MS.^[13]
- **Saponins, Resins, Glycosides:** Saponins, resinous compounds and various glycosides (possibly cardiac glycosides) are reported in different parts.^[1,9] These may underlie surfactant-like or cytotoxic effects.
- **Others:** Cotton pigments like gossypapurins and carotenoids (from seed) and small peptides (Phytochemical studies using tests and spectroscopy confirm these groups. For example, early screening of the flower or leaf shows carbohydrates, flavonoids, tannins, steroids, terpenoids, saponins, resins, and proteins.^[3,6] Acid hydrolysis has been used to identify proanthocyanidins in leaf extracts. identify proanthocyanidins in leaf extract.^[4]

7.3 Methods of Phytochemical Analysis

Standard analytical procedures have been used. Water, methanol/ethanol (for phenolics and glycosides), and hexane/chloroform (for lipids and terpenoids) are common polar solvents used in extraction. For example, Larayetan et al. extracted *G. herbaceum* leaves using ethanol and hexane for GC-MS profiling. Chromatography and spectrometry are often utilised: GC-MS identified hundreds of volatiles and fatty acids,^[13] while HPLC was used to quantify flavonoids and gossypol in cotton. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC/HPTLC) allows for fingerprinting: an HPTLC profile of *G. herbaceum* flower under UV radiation (254/366 nm) with vanillin-sulfuric acid derivatisation produced distinct R_f spots for phenolics and terpenoids.^[6] These fingerprints serve as quality assurance standards. Physicochemical tests (loss on drying, ash values, extractive values) have also been conducted for various parts^[6,9] assisting with uniformity.

Pharmacological Activities

Each major activity of *G. herbaceum* has been validated in laboratory experiments, often supported by mechanistic insights.

- **Antioxidant:** Leaf and seed extracts show strong radical-scavenging effects. Ethanol and hexane extracts of leaves had DPPH• and nitric oxide scavenging IC₅₀ values in the low µg/mL range (~3–5 µg/mL).^[13] These effects are associated with total phenolic/flavonoid content. The high levels of polyphenols (gossypol, quercetin, etc.) transfer electrons to neutralise free radicals, which is likely responsible for the reported protection against oxidative stress in cells.
- **Antimicrobial:** *G. herbaceum* exhibits broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity. Flavonoid-rich fractions from seed and callus cultures inhibited the fungus *Trichoderma viride* and bacteria such as *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *E. coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium*.^[16] Similarly, crude ethanol/hexane leaf extracts significantly inhibited multidrug-resistant bacterial strains.^[13] The antibacterial impact is due to phenolics and gossypol, which can destroy microbial membranes and proteins.
- **Anti-inflammatory:** Animal studies indicate potent anti-inflammatory/anti-arthritic properties. In an adjuvant-induced arthritis rat model, daily treatment (10–28 days) with *G. herbaceum* methanol leaf extract (200 mg/kg) significantly reduced paw swelling, erythema and joint inflammation, restoring weight and haematological parameters.^[17] This suggests suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines or mediators. Although exact pathways are not fully defined, related cotton studies have shown that gossypol can inhibit NF-κB activation. Thus, the plant's flavonoids and gossypol likely contribute to reducing TNF-α/IL-1β-driven inflammation.^[2,17]
- **Anti-arthritic:** Overlapping with anti-inflammatory, specific anti-arthritic efficacy was demonstrated in the same arthritis model. The extract substantially improved arthritic symptoms, demonstrating genuine disease-modifying potential. In treated animals, antioxidant levels (e.g., catalase and SOD) were restored, and inflammatory markers were reduced, suggesting the need for more mechanistic studies.^[17]
- **Antidiabetic/Hypolipidemic:** Multiple studies show blood-glucose-lowering and lipid-improving effects. In alloxan-induced diabetic rats, 200 mg/kg of ethanol or ether leaf extract lowered fasting glucose by ~30–40% within weeks and normalised insulin/glucose markers.^[18] It also significantly reduced serum triglycerides, LDL, VLDL and total cholesterol while raising HDL. Similar results were seen in dexamethasone-hyperglycemic rats and in rabbits treated with seed extracts.^[19] These effects are ascribed to enzyme

inhibition (e.g. α -amylase, α -glucosidase) and improved peripheral glucose uptake by flavonoids/tannins.^[18,19,20] The synergy of its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions may further protect pancreatic β -cells.

- **Antiulcer:** Oral administration of 250-500 mg/kg ethanolic leaf extract effectively protected ethanol-induced gastric ulcers in rats, comparable to standard lansoprazole.^[21] Histological examination revealed rapid mucosal healing due to flavonoids and tannins, which increase mucus production and block ulcerogenic agents. The extract reduced gastric acidity, indicating an inhibitory action on H^+ - K^+ ATPase similar to that of established phytotherapeutics.

- **Diuretic:** Ethanol and ethyl acetate leaf extracts (100–200 mg/kg) markedly increased urine volume and excretion of Na^+ , K^+ ions in rats (similar to furosemide).^[22] This diuretic effect likely involves complex actions of alkaloids and steroids, which alter renal tubular function and electrolyte transport. The phytochemicals (flavonoids, tannins) may inhibit tubular reabsorption of sodium and chloride.

- **Antiepileptic:** Both aqueous and chloroform leaf extracts (10-100 mg/kg) exhibited significant, dose-dependent anticonvulsant effects, surpassing the reference medicines phenobarbitone and diazepam.^[23] In pentylenetetrazole and maximal electroshock seizure models, treated rats showed reduced convulsions. This mechanism appears to include potentiation of GABAergic neurotransmission: in vitro studies indicate that the flavonoid gossypin increases GABA_A receptor activity and modifies glycine receptor function.^[15] This GABA-facilitating activity is likely responsible for the extract's anti-seizure efficacy.^[15,23]

- **Antifertility:** Methanolic extracts of *G. herbaceum* root (2.2-3.0 g/kg/day in rats) had significant antifertility effects. Females that were treated showed a reduction in healthy ovarian follicles (particularly Graafian follicles and corpora lutea), an increase in atretic follicles, and significantly lower uterine and ovarian weights and lining thickness.^[10] These atrophic changes indicate that phytochemicals (particularly gossypol and related terpenoids) affect ovarian folliculogenesis and hormonal homeostasis. Cottonseed extracts were previously studied as male contraceptives for this reason.

- **Anthelmintic:** In vitro assays using earthworms showed that ethanol and ether leaf extracts are lethal to worms at 60–100 mg/mL, comparable to albendazole (10 mg/mL).^[24] The ether

extract had more potency. Phytosterols and tannins are likely to damage the worm's tegument and its metabolism, leading to paralysis and death.

- **Antiuro lithiatic:** Ethanolic and aqueous leaf extracts effectively dissolve calcium oxalate kidney stones *in vitro*.^[25] The ethanol extract showed a higher dissolution rate, comparable to that of standard herbal medicine ("Neeri"). This activity is attributed to saponins and glycosides, which may chelate calcium and inhibit crystal development, hence reducing stone formation.

- **Wound Healing:** Topical administration of 200 mg/kg methanolic leaf extract improved wound healing in rat models. Treated wounds epithelialized faster and took less time to heal, while the repaired skin's tensile strength increased. Flavonoids and tannins (which have antioxidant and antibacterial properties) stimulate collagen production and help prevent infection, allowing for faster repair.^[26]

Mechanism of Action

The pharmacological effects of *G. herbaceum* derive from its diverse phytochemicals, which act on multiple molecular targets. Key mechanisms include:

- **Antioxidant pathways:** Polyphenols (gossypol, flavonoids) donate electrons to neutralise ROS (e.g. DPPH•, NO•), chelate metal catalysts, and upregulate endogenous antioxidants (SOD, CAT).^[13] This explains the extensive protective benefits (anti-inflammatory, wound healing).

- **Enzyme modulation:** Flavonoids and tannins may inhibit carbohydrate-hydrolysing enzymes, including α -amylase and α -glucosidase, leading to antidiabetic benefits. *In vitro* studies on *G. herbaceum* leaf powder revealed significant inhibition of α -amylase and α -glucosidase (48.5% and 30.7%, respectively)^[27] (abstract data). Similarly, phenolics' inhibition of cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase is likely responsible for their anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects.

- **Neurotransmitter modulation:** Flavonoids, such as gossypin, can enhance GABAergic signalling while inhibiting excitatory transmission.^[15] This explains the anticonvulsant properties. Gossypol and other lignans may also alter serotonergic and dopaminergic systems, as evidenced by claimed antidepressant effects.

- **Anti-inflammatory signalling:** Gossypol has been shown (in related species) to suppress NF- κ B activation, reducing pro-inflammatory cytokines. In *G. herbaceum* studies, reversal of arthritis was accompanied by decreased inflammatory markers, implicating interference with pathways such as NF- κ B and COX-2.^[18] Flavonoids also reduce TNF- α and IL-1 β production.
- **Metabolic regulation:** *G. herbaceum* extracts may improve lipid metabolism and insulin sensitivity through AMPK/GLUT4 pathways, potentially reversing hyperlipidemia and hyperglycemia.^[18,19] Steroidal saponins may influence cholesterol metabolism, as evidenced by their lipid-lowering actions.
- **Cellular toxicity and fertility:** The bis-aldehyde structure of gossypol makes it reactive with amines, inhibiting dehydrogenases and uncoupling oxidative phosphorylation.^[3,14] This nonspecific cytotoxicity explains its anti-fertility (oocyte/follicle degeneration) and anti-cancer potential. Gossypol can create Schiff bases with proteins and DNA, influencing cell proliferation.

In summary, compounds from *G. herbaceum* work by scavenging free radicals, inhibiting enzymes, modulating receptors (such as GABA), and affecting cell signaling pathways. These actions explain the plant's wide range of pharmacological effects.

Toxicological Studies and Safety Profile

Toxicological data on *G. herbaceum* are limited; safety concerns primarily focus on gossypol. Gossypol is known to cause toxicity at high dosages (e.g., infertility, hypokalemia, and gastrointestinal distress). Its two reactive aldehyde groups make it chemically active.^[3,14] In animal feeding studies, persistent high consumption of raw cottonseed produces cardiotoxicity and liver damage due to gossypol. However, properly processed extracts and defatted seeds (with less gossypol) are much safer. Most *in vivo* experiments show no obvious acute toxicity at therapeutic dosages (up to several hundred mg/kg).^[18,10] Nevertheless, caution is advised: excessive consumption can lead to cardiotoxicity and respiratory distress (as demonstrated in livestock fed cottonseed).^[3,14] No controlled human safety studies are available. Thus, while the plant has an adequate safety margin in animal models, more chronic toxicity and teratogenicity investigations are required. Traditional use (such as low-dose seed infusions) is currently considered safe, although no regulatory dosage restrictions have been established.

Pharmacognostic and Standardisation Studies

Pharmacognostic investigations have established macroscopy, microscopy and quality standards for *G. herbaceum*. Macroscopically, essential features include lobed leaves, a hairy stem, yellow-purple flowers, and black seeds (see Botanical Description above). Microscopic diagnoses include:

- **Root TS:** features a single-layered cork, dense pericycle fibres, radial phloem bands, and prominent lysigenous cavities in the cortex.
- **Powder:** contains numerous lignified fibres, stone cells, spiral-pitted and annular vessel elements, and calcium oxalate rosettes and prisms; starch grains are rare.^[9]
- **Leaf TS:** (not described in sources) most likely exhibits typical *Malvaceae* characteristics such as palisade and spongy mesophyll, stellate hairs, and glandular trichomes.

Physicochemical constants have been established, with flower drugs containing around 10.4% total ash, 0.48% acid-insoluble ash, and 6.75% alcohol-soluble extractive.^[6] To be considered pure, a leaf/flower or root powder should meet requirements for moisture (loss on drying ~6-11%)^[6,9] ash (5-10%), and extractive levels. HPTLC and TLC fingerprints are used to ensure quality control. One HPTLC chromatogram of flower ethanol extract (UV 254 nm) revealed significant spots at R_f ~0.04 and 0.50 (change after derivatisation).^[6] Similarly, TLC of leaves showed UV-induced flavonoid and gossypol stains. These chromatographic profiles, along with certain physicochemical parameters, serve as reference standards. Overall, standardisation of *G. herbaceum* involves macroscopic (size, colour), microscopic (cell types), physicochemical (ash, extractives) and chromatographic (fingerprint) parameters to ensure identity and purity.

Clinical Studies

So far, there have been no published clinical trials on *G. herbaceum*. All current evidence comes from in vitro or animal studies, so its safety and effectiveness in humans still need to be confirmed. Some related Gossypium products, like cottonseed oil, are used in food, but there is no clinical data on specific therapeutic extracts of *G. herbaceum*. This is a major gap, and traditional claims (such as for lactation or diabetes) need thorough clinical testing.

Industrial and Pharmaceutical Applications

Beyond traditional treatment, *G. herbaceum* has emerging applications. Cotton fibre (cellulose) is a major textile fibre, and its antibacterial properties (due to surface-bound gossypol) are being used in functional fabrics. Cottonseed oil (after degossypolization) is used both as an edible oil and a vitamin E supplement. Defatted cottonseed meal, high in protein and free of gossypol, is being studied as an animal feed and a nutraceutical. Because of their strong bioactivities, gossypol and its derivatives have been studied as male contraceptives and anticancer agents in drug development. According to laboratory investigations, *G. herbaceum* extracts could be made into herbal tonics or ointments (for example, to cure wounds), with its bioactive components (flavonoids, terpenoids) serving as lead molecules. Recent reviews even include the application of Gossypium ingredients in advanced materials, such as cotton-derived cellulose nanocrystals for drug delivery and fibres modified with plant-based compounds for medical textiles.^[2] In conclusion, *G. herbaceum* has potential in pharmaceuticals (antimicrobials, antioxidants), nutraceuticals (fibre, oil, and protein supplements), and as a source of green polymers and bio-inspired materials.

Research Gaps and Future Perspectives

Although preclinical research is promising, important gaps remain. There are few human clinical trials to confirm its effectiveness and safety for conditions like diabetes, arthritis, and wound healing. Standardisation of extracts, such as measuring marker chemicals like gossypol and gossypin, is still lacking. More needs to be learned about how it works, especially the exact molecular targets of its antidiabetic and anti-inflammatory effects. Further research is needed to isolate and study new compounds, such as minor terpenoids or alkaloids, and to understand their structure-activity relationships. Comparing *G. herbaceum* with related species like *G. arboreum* may reveal better types. Sustainable cultivation (with low-gossypol varieties) and safety studies (on long-term toxicity and reproductive effects) are also needed. As Reddy and Akondi said, "the plant proved useful... and further studies in this direction are necessary to understand its mechanism."^[17] Addressing these gaps will help validate and safely use *G. herbaceum* as a therapy.

CONCLUSION

In summary, *Gossypium herbaceum* (Kapās or Levant cotton) is a valuable medicinal plant with many bioactive compounds. Research has confirmed several of its traditional uses, such as its strong antioxidant, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antidiabetic effects.^[1,2] These benefits come from ingredients like gossypol and flavonoids, which work through different

mechanisms. The plant's versatility makes it a promising and affordable herbal remedy, especially in developing countries. However, more detailed pharmacological and clinical studies, as well as better standardisation, are needed. Because of its bioactive properties, *G. herbaceum* deserves further study as a source of new natural medicines and nutraceuticals.

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